

Is Fermat's Least Time Principle Equivalent to a Least Information Approach? Part 2

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In Part 1, we suggested that Fermat's Least Time Principle is equivalent to a least information in space approach, where spatial information is given by length / (\hbar/p) or px . Here we note that given the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, one actually has minimal information in both space and time. For a fixed E (E is the same in both n_1 and n_2 regions for refraction) in Et , it seems that one minimizes time, but one actually minimizes time/ (\hbar/E). Independently in terms of time and space, one minimizes information. This leads to a consistent picture (which may use either space or time) we argue and also one that is statistical as opposed to the notion of minimizing time for no particular reason.

Given that we use the notion of special relativity above, we try to see how this theory is linked to minimization of information. In another note (1), we showed that one may use $F=dp/dt$ to derive the form $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. $g(v)$ appears in the comparison of physics in a rest frame and one moving with $-v$, but it is $F=dp/dt$ (a Newtonian vector equation) which fixes its functional form. Given $F=dp/dt$, one is forced to focus on conservation of momentum and projections in 3-space. We note, however, that special relativity yields $E=[p] c$ for $m_0=0$. Here $[p]$ is the magnitude which is rotationally invariant like E . Given $x=vt$, one may write: $-Et+px = 0$ for a photon. Here $p=[p]$.

As a result, one seems to have two very different ideas present, we argue. First, $F=dp/dt$, a vector equation, deals with components and conservation of momentum for various components. $-Et+[p]x=0$, however, is an equation which lies along the direction of motion, regardless of whether momentum is conserved in this direction. It is analogous to a wave equation with arguments $-wt+x/\lambda=0$. If there really were a physical connection, then conservation of momentum in a particular direction would be akin to Newtonian mechanics, while $-Et+[p]x=0$ might be akin to wave mechanics. In Part 1, however, we treated the wave mechanics features as information without mentioning the word wave. It seems that $-Et+[p]x = 0$ is linked with physical behaviour along the direction of motion, and conservation of momentum in one direction (not x) is a consequence. We suggest that a priori one might wish to follow a particle along its direction of motion and have a theory which is based only on numbers, not vectors. This, we argue, is the information theory introduced in Part 1, i.e. minimization of information in either t or x . Here we note that there are in fact two minimizations of information, one in time $t / (\hbar/E)$ and one in space $x / (\hbar/p)$.

We apply this reasoning to two dimensional refraction (Snell's law) and note that particle behaviour only appears when one considers projections to obtain conservation of momentum parallel to the n_1 - n_2 medium interface.

Minimal Time Might be Minimal Information in Time

In Part 1, we suggested that Fermat's Least Time Principle is equivalent to a minimization of information in space, i.e.

$$px = x / (1/p) \quad ((1))$$

We note that information is linked to statistics and is also a number, i.e. not based on vectors. We suggest that these are two important ideas as we try to argue that one may avoid vector projections by introducing such a number based (information) statistical theory to describe refraction (Snell's law). In other words, we do wish to start with the a priori statement:

Motion minimizes time because there does not seem to be any reason for this ((2))

Rather, we suggest that statistically there is a reason for minimal information. It is the basic idea used in Maxwell-Boltzmann theory as long as some constraints are respected. We suggest that the notion of "minimum" in Fermat's principle should really apply to information in time or in space.

Special Relativity

We showed in (1), that if one compares a rest frame (particle with m_0 at $x=0, t$) from a frame moving at $-v$, there is E, p, x', t' . If one suggests that:

$$E = m_0 c^2 g(v) \quad p = m_0 v g(v) \quad ((2))$$

then one may determine $g(v)$ using $F = dp/dt$ and ((2)). In other words, Newton's second law is key and it is linked with conservation of energy and momentum as well as vectors. This seems to be a very different scenario from the number (informatio) based theory described in the above paragraph.

Special relativity, however, also yields the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et + [p]x \quad ((3))$$

Here $[p]$ is the magnitude of p and x is the direction of motion, so there is really one spatial dimension in ((3)) (even though one may make various projections).

((3)) leads to the notion of solving physical problems by using one dimension so to speak, the dimension of the trajectory. This approach, however, must be compatible with vector projections because $F = dp/dt$ (a vector equation) is used to derive $g(v)$ of special relativity. This, we suggest, is the particle-wave duality of quantum mechanics, but we will explain this in more detail.

A physical wave follows

$$\text{Speed} = x/t = \text{frequency} * \text{wavelength} \quad \text{and} \quad x = \text{speed} * t \quad ((4)) \text{ so}$$

$$-\text{frequency} t + x/\text{wavelength} = 0 \quad ((5))$$

((3)) is of the same form as ((5)), but this does not prove that one has a physical wave. Mathematically, however, one may make a direct connection. One might ask: Why? We suggest that this allows for a one dimension in space - number (information) based theory of solving a problem. We consider refraction (Snell's law) as an example.

Snell's Law from a Number (information) -One Dimension in Space Approach

It is well-known that if one has an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction interface at $y=0$, along the x axis, then:

$$p_1 \sin(\theta_1) = p_2 \sin(\theta_2) = \text{conservation of momentum along the } x \text{ axis} \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{Here } p_1 = p \cdot n_1 \text{ and } p_2 = p \cdot n_2 \quad ((7))$$

This is a Newtonian type approach to solving the problem and we argue that there is nothing wrong with it. It uses the idea of projections in 3-space. We suggest, however, that one may solve the problem by considering only motion along the trajectory and information as a number. This we call a duality for solving the problem. We use ((3)) for this approach and so it seems that

$$\text{In time one has } t / (1/E) \text{ and in space, } x / (1/p) \quad ((8))$$

If one minimizes either of these (which are both equivalent) then

$$\text{Minimize: } p_1 \sqrt{y^2 + x^2} + p_2 \sqrt{y^2 + (L-x)^2} \quad ((9))$$

This is equivalent to minimizing a number while only considering length in space (a one dimensional concept) regardless of whether the length lies in 2-space. ((9)) leads to Snell's law. Thus, one can solve Snell's law using what we call the quantum particle-wave duality, although instead of a physical wave, we think in terms of information which may be linked to probability for momentum hits in space or interactions. Thus, the quantum

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((10))$$

is a complex probability which yields a probability for an E interaction at t or a p impulse hit at x .

As a result, one may use a deterministic theory and consider conservation of momentum along various projections in 3-space or one may consider a number based (information) theory linked to motion along a trajectory. This allows one to minimize information in either time or space, and this approach appears to be statistical. Thus, there is a particle (deterministic-projection in 3-space) approach which yields the same results as a statistical, minimization of information in space approach.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part 1, we argued that minimization of time in Fermat's Least Time Principle is equivalent to minimization of information in space. Here we argue that one ultimately minimizes a number (information) either in space or time. It is really the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ that one considers. For refraction (Snell's law), E is constant in both index of refraction regions and so it seems that one is simply minimizing time. We argue that really one minimizes $t / (1/E)$ for time or $x / (1/p)$ for space. This leads to a consistent picture which is based on minimal information or statistics. To develop such a viewpoint, we start with special relativity.

Special relativity (Lorentz transformation) may be developed using the notion of a particle at rest at $x=0$, t (rest mass m_0) as seen by a frame moving at $-v$. Then: $E = \gamma(v)m_0c^2$ and $p = \gamma(v)m_0v$, but $\gamma(v)$ is unknown. In (2), we showed that one may use $F=dp/dt$ (a Newtonian vector equation) to find $\gamma(v)$. Thus, the notion of conservation of p and vector projections must be considered valid. At the same time, the Lorentz invariant: $-Et + [p]x$ is also valid and only deals with one dimension in space (the trajectory). We suggest that one should be able to solve a problem (e.g. refraction and Snell's law) either using Newtonian conservation of momentum and projections, or the number (information) based equation $-Et + [p]x$.

The question then becomes: How does one solve the problem in the latter case? We suggest that $-Et+[p]x = 0$ follows from $E=pc$ ($m_0=0$ i.e a photon) and $x=ct$. One may consider $1/E$ as information in time or $1/[p]$ as information in space. Minimizing either yields Snell's law as we show. Alternatively, one may use conservation of momentum for the Newtonian projection of p along the n_1 - n_2 surface. This we call quantum particle wave duality. The wave part, we argue, does not concern a physical wave, but rather information, i.e. a probability wave. The information may be linked to points in t,x at which E interacts or p renders an impulse hit, i.e. $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is such a probability, although being complex.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Lagrangian Theory from Special Relativity? (preprint, zenodo, 2026)